

EFFECT OF BYPASS FAT FEEDING ON FEED INTAKE AND CORRELATION WITH MILK PRODUCTION AND BODY CONDITIONS OF CROSS BREED LACTATING COWS IN COASTAL DISTRICT OF ODISHA

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Abstract

A total of sixty reproductive crossbred cows were selected for this experiment which were divided into two groups in equal numbers of 30 animals in each. Animals in control group (C) were maintained as per the traditional practices of the farmer where as treatment groups were fed bypass fat @ 200 g along with mineral mixture 100gm per day for 45 days per animal in (T₁) group. The performances were measured in terms of milk yield, fat percentage; SNF percentage and price of milk realized by the farmers and net return were calculated. The average daily gain in milk per animal, fat percentage and SNF percentage of the treatment group differed significantly at (p<0.05) from the control group. Higher percentage of fat, SNF in milk and net return was achieved in treated group followed by control group. Due to increase in fat and SNF % percentage in milk the price realized by the dairy farmers was higher as compared to control group. The higher percentage of milk yield and milk Fat % was in treated group. It may be concluded that mineral mixture and bypass fat supplementation increased milk yield and fat percentage of milk and milk price of crossbred cows, which increased dairy farmer's net return.

Key word : By pass fat feeding, Mineral Mixtutre, Fat supplementation Cross breed cow, Body condition score

Introduction

The diet of high producing crossbred cows is usually deficient in energy during transition period (3 weeks before and after parturition) and early lactation. The animals are not able to eat more during advanced stage of pregnancy; therefore we need to increase the energy density of their ration with minimal changes in dietary forage to concentrate ratio and fiber intake. It improves the energy balance that leads to an improvement in reproductive efficiency and the metabolic health of the cow. Fat supplementation has little effects on rumen fermentation, as indicated by the acetate to propionate ratio but the fat from different sources had variable effects. Unsaturated fatty acids, especially in the non-esterified form, are toxic to rumen microbes and may decrease fiber degradation in the rumen. If the energy dense ration is not offered to the animals then they may lose more body weight after parturition due to negative energy balance (NEBAL). Such animals are very weak and come into heat with great difficulty. They are also prone to several metabolic disorders like fatty liver, ketosis, displaced abomasums etc. The delayed conception in such cases leads to longer inter-calving periods in cows. These animals produce less milk after parturition which leads to great economic losses to the dairy farmers.

There is a practice of offering raw vegetable oils to cows by our farmers which is not reasonable. Just 2% vegetable oil in the diet can dramatically reduce rumen fiber digestion. Unprotected fats cause physical and chemical changes in the microbial fermentation of the feed and depress rumen cellulolytic microbial activity. The supplementation of the raw vegetable oils is detrimental for the health of cows after a certain limit as it affects the digestion of fibers adversely in the rumen. Therefore, we need to supplement fats in such a way that it doesn't interfere with its digestion in the rumen. Rumen bypass or "protected" fats are in fact, the dry fats which are processed to be easily handled and mixed into all animal feeds. Dry fats are mostly insoluble at rumen body temperature due to the high melting points. Dietary fat, which resists lipolysis and bio hydrogenation in rumen by rumen microorganisms, but gets digested in lower digestive tract, is known as bypass fat or rumen protected fat or inert fat. Rumen by-pass or 'protected' fats are dry fats that are processed to be easily mixed into animal feeds.

Bypass fat is generally used to increase the energy density in the ration of cows. Bypass fat gets digested later in the abomasum or true stomach of ruminants as it is not affected by the rumen microbes. Thus bypass fats are very useful in improving not only the body condition score of the weaker animals but also increase the productivity of milk. Bypass fats are made up of fatty acids linked to calcium ions instead of glycerol backbone. By virtue of this association bypass fat becomes inert to the rumen microbes and

escapes fermentation. It has low solubility and less susceptible to bio-hydrogenation by microbes. The interaction between nutrition and reproduction has long been known to have important implications for the reproductive performance in animals. Supplementation of fat, minerals and vitamins in the diet led to improvement in reproductive efficiency in cattle (Ramteke *et al.*, 2004). Under nutrition results in the loss of body weight and body condition leading to negative energy balance (Bindari *et al.*, 2013). Bypass fat has low solubility in rumen and is less susceptible to bio hydrogenation. However, in abomasum at acidic pH it is dissociated and set free fatty acids and calcium for absorption. Initially, the role of protected fat was considered only as an energy supplement during the transition period leading to improvement in reproductive performance, but later on, it was demonstrated that the effect was also due to fatty acids which act as a precursor of progesterone via cholesterol and prostaglandins (Staples *et al.*, 1998).

The advantages of bypass fat feeding

By pass fat feeding increases the amount of energy in the feed so that the animals seldom come under negative energy balance especially during the period of transition and early lactation. also it meets the energy requirements of the high producing animals without any problem.

Feeding by Pass fat not only increases the milk production but also improves the persistency of lactation. Animals in positive energy balance have better reproduction ability through early heat symptoms and better conception rate. It increases the overall productive life of animals and helps to control many metabolic disorders like ketosis and milk fever in the high producing animals. Bypass fat feeding can positively affect the efficiency of dairy cows through a combination of caloric and non-caloric effects. Energy density of the ration of lactating animals is low in developing countries and it is not able to meet energy requirements after calving as dry matter intake during this period (8-10 week) is low. This leads to substantial loss in body weight which adversely affects production and reproduction in dairy animals. Energy density of ration can be increased by incorporating bypass fat in ration of lactating animals. Bypass fat is inert in the rumen and good source of fatty acids for meeting energy needs of animals and fatty acids requirement for meat synthesis. (Garg, N.R. and Mehta, A.K. 1998). The milk yield is increased by 5.5-24.0% along with the improvement in post partum recovery of the body weight and body condition score and reproductive performance of the dairy animals. Feeding of the indigenously prepared bypass fat to lactating dairy animals has shown to give additional benefit of Rs. 12-40/- per animal per day (Naik, P.K. 2013).

Objectives

The milk yield and fat percentage is based on genetic potential of a cow, we cannot increase the milk yield beyond its genetic potential. But most dairy farmers in India do not even get the actual potential milk yield from their dairy animals. The primary reason for this is malnutrition as well as the dairy cattle are put into various stress factors. So the easiest way to increase the milk yields to address the nutritional requirements as well as address the stress factors. The market price of milk procured by milk societies or collection centers is determined by the percentage of milk solids (fat content, SNF content) in the milk, higher the milk solid percentage higher is the market price. Fat and SNF content in milk of lactating cows depends upon breed of animal and can be maintained by balanced feeding (dry fodder, green fodder, compound cattle feed or concentrates and mineral mixtures) to meet its requirements. Solids Not Fat (SNF) consists of everything except milk fat and water. That means total solids content in the entire residue left after complete evaporation of water from milk. This includes fat protein, lactose and mineral matter. Normally cow milk contains 8.5% SNF. Proper feeding management in dairy cows is one of the vital factors that will yield better milk production with maximum Fat and SNF content. Knowledge on nutrient requirement and balanced nutrition will improve the productivity of animals. Due to high price of raw materials and lack of scientific farming knowledge, the cost of production of milk is increasing a day by day. Increasing milk fat and Solids Not Fat (SNF) level in milk will increase the selling price for milk and thus maximise profit in dairy farming. SNF can be defined as the remaining constituents of milk other than fat. They are tested by using lactometer. Fixation of price to milk is being done by taking into consideration both fat and SNF content of milk. In India, most of the dairy farmers are small and marginal, (Naik et al., 2013) and often, bypass fat is out of reach to them due to its inadequate accessibility or high cost. By keeping in view the above aspects, the present study has been undertaken to assess effect of bypass fat feeding on milk composition, change in FAT percentage of milk and milk yield and daily income from milk in cows kept in homestead

conditions. The present study was planned to accumulate data on efficacy of bypass fat feeding with mineral mixtures on milk yield and milk fat percentage and to identify the various problems perceived relating to increase in production cost and other inputs like feed cost, marketing aspects confronted by dairy farmers of the district.

Materials and Methods

The district of Jagatsinghpur lies in the agro-climatic zone of east and south east coastal plain zone of Odisha extending from 20-21^o North latitude to 84-87^o East longitude. The district consists of eight blocks i.e. Jagatsinghpur, Raghunathapur, Balikuda, Biridi, Naugaon, Tirtol, Kujanga and Erasama. Animal husbandry and dairy development have recognized as important economic activities in Jagatsinghpur district. Next to agriculture, livestock supports the farmers to generate income and employment.

Livestock Production had always been an integral part of the rural livelihood systems in Odisha, all through the known history of the state. The predominant farming system in Odisha is the mixed crop-livestock farming system and over 90 per cent of farmers of all categories conform to this farming system. The livestock wealth of Odisha is impressive in numbers across all species, constituting a natural resource base with immense livelihood implications, even though productivity levels are very low. Livestock holding in Orissa is equitable as over 80 per cent of all livestock are owned by the marginal / small holders and the land less. Some 80 per cent of all rural households own livestock of one species or the other, or a combination of some of them, Cattle being the most popular and therefore, the preponderant species. This sector is a major contributor to rural employment next to agriculture. Odisha contributed about 6.09 percent of cattle population in the country being 7th in India. The live stock production system has been an integral part of the rural livelihood system contributing significantly for poverty reduction in the country. It is observed that the contribution of agriculture sector to gross domestic product (GDP) has been declining trend where as the contribution from livestock sector has been increasing.

Table 1: Livestock Information status of the Jagatsinghpur district (Census year 2012)

Name of The Block	Cattle (Nos)			Buffaloes (Nos)		
	Cross Bred	Indigenous	Total	Improved	Indigenous	Total
Balikuda	38696	10966	49662	*	2686	2686
Biridi	18287	5473	23760	*	137	137
Ersama	8458	38452	46910	*	694	694
Jagatsinghpur	30038	8179	38217	*	689	689
Kujang	20844	22901	43745	*	2401	2401
Naugaon	20642	4978	25620	*	1172	1172
Raghunathpur	15768	5016	20,784	*	503	503
Tirtol	19530	22995	42525	*	3076	3076
Total	172263	118960	291223	*	11358	11358

Source- Comprehensive District Plan (2015-16) for Jagatsinghpur District

From the above table it was found that most of the farmers are rearing crossbred cows in the district. Cross breed cow's population was about 60 percent of total cow population of the district. The cross

breed cows' population was found comparatively higher in two selected blocks Kujanga and Tirtol in the district.

Table 2. Trend analysis of milk Production and Productivity during the last four years in the district

Name of commodity	Baseline (2011-12)			2012-13 (Actual)			2013-14 (Actual)			2014-15 (Actual)		
	Nos	Product ion	Product ivity	Nos	Produc tion	Producti vity	Nos	Produc tion	Producti vity	Nos	Product ion	Producti vity
Milk	137554	94.23 TMT	7 lts/day	144434	96.6 TMT	7.1 lts/day	151656	100.2T MT	7.2 lts/day	159239	102.0 TMT	7.3 lts/day

The milk productivity of cow in Jagatsinghpur district is (7.3 kg/day) day as compared to state average (6.18 kg/day). The sector has ample scope to substantially enhance the production to meet the domestic

market demands, create employment and income generating opportunities for the rural poor and enhance their food and livelihood security.

Multistage sampling design was used in selection of the district, block and village and cattle owners. In the first stage Jagatsinghpur district was purposively selected on the basis of live stock population, as the district has large population of livestock, good track record of artificial insemination and the average milk yield for cross bred cows of the district (7.3 kg/day). In the second stage blocks like Tirtol and Kujanga blocks were selected purposively as per the highest cattle population in these two blocks and most of the farmer's livelihood pattern depend upon diary sector and animal husbandry is the major share of their family income. Three number of adopted villages of Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Jagatsinghpur namely Nagapura, and Zillanasi of Tirtol blok and Bagoi in Kujanga block were selected randomly where the on farm trials on assessment of bypass fat feeding in milching cows were conducted in year 2015-16 and 2016-17. In the fourth stage ten cattle owners were selected purposively from each of the selected villages having CB cows, those were involved during the above on farm trial (OFT) process. Purposive sampling is a non probability sampling method in which subjects are selected according to specific criteria established by the investigator. Thus non-probability purposive sampling was found to be appropriate for study. Thus in all thirty cattle owners having one or more number of CB cows were selected purposively from three villages for the present study and a total 60 numbers of CB cows were taken as sample size for this study. A total of sixty reproductive crossbreed milching cows were selected for this experiment which were divided among two groups in equal numbers of 30 animals in each. Animals in control group (T₁) were maintained as per the traditional practices of the farmer where as treatment groups were fed with bypass fat @ 200 g per day per animal along with mineral mixture @ 100 g per day per animal in (T₂) group with having similar feeding conditions. Cows having similar body weight 300 kg, cow in 2nd or 3rd parity, with previous history of milk production in range of 7-10 kg/day in previous lactation, with no history of metabolic diseases, within 3 months of calving, having similar feeding conditions (stall feeding with green grasses 14-15 kg/day, paddy straw 5-6 kg/day, concentrate 3.5-4 kg/day) were selected for this study. The animals were de wormed with Fenbendazole @ 7.5 mg/kg body weight and the trial was started 5 days post de worming. The cow owners were provided with commercial bypass fat powder (Fatomax®) and Minerals like mineral mixture (Minfa Gold®). The cows under treatment group were fed bypass fat @200gm/day and mineral mixture @ 100gm/day in two equal doses.

Cows in control group(C) was fed required amount of concentrate mixture as per their body weight and production performance and paddy straw, while in another treatment group(T₁) the same control diet was supplemented with 200 g of fat/head/ day and mineral mixtures 100 gram mineral mixture per head per day. Milk production from individual animal was recorded daily during milking i.e. morning at 7 a.m. and evening at 5.30 p.m...

The following treatments were made to the selected cows under trials and the treatment was, feeding bypass fat (Fatomax marketed by Intas Pharmaceutical Ltd. Matoda, Ahmedabad, India) 200 gram per day per animal for 45 days. Along with 100 gram mineral mixture per day (Minfa Gold marketed by Intas Pharmaceutical Ltd. Matoda, Ahmedabad, India) orally daily for 45 days. along with normal stall feeding with green grass, and concentrate as normal procedure.

Under on-farm trial programme conducted by KVK, Jagatsinghpur, cattle owners were being provided with Fatomax and Minerals and

Table 3 – Effect of bypass fat and mineral mixture feed on milk yield,

Attributes	Milk yield (lit)/ cow / day		“t” cal Value	“t” table value	p value
	Control group	Treatment group			
Milk production for first 3 months	15.2	17.6	5.103*	2.045	0.00
Variance	2.082	4.313			
Standard Error	0.258	0.372			

advised to feed the cows at 200 gram per day per animal for 45 days along with 100 gram mineral mixture per day for 45 days along with the rate of per cent of daily ration on dry matter intake basis along with mineral mixture supplement, and concentrate on daily basis to the selected thirty numbers of CB cows under trials and the proper feed management practices were adopted by the farmers as per the recommendation. All the cows were fed with similar ration as per requirements and cows with experimental group were fed with 200 gm by pass fat daily in the morning along with cattle feed and fodder. Animals had free access to clean drinking water. The milk yield per head per day or productivity, fat percentage, SNF %, selling price of milk according to FAT and SNF percentage was recorded regularly upto three months post calving and parameters measured were compared with both control and treatment groups. Fat % in milk was estimated once in a ten days using electronic milko tester manufactured by “Neel Electricals & Electronics Jaipur (Rajasthan, India). The price of milk in rupees per Kg, economics and the variable cost incurred, gross return and net return were calculated for each milching cow. In the study area the farmers were supplying the milk to co-operative societies and the cost of milk was decided by the societies as per the fat percentage recorded. The constraints associated with production system and marketing perceived by the farmers were recorded from individual respondents. For construction of interview schedule, information regarding the constraints faced by the farmers was collected and necessary addition and deletions were made after pre-test. The schedule was administered by personal interview method. The selected dairy farmers as respondents were asked to answer each items or constraints faced as always, sometimes and never and score assigned were 2, 1, 0 respectively. Data were collected by personal interview with the help of pre tested interview schedule in 2017 and the collected data were coded, classified, tabulated and analyzed by using statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, percentage, correlation coefficient “r” and Fisher's ‘t’ test for two independent samples were employed, wherever found appropriate to draw valid conclusion. Fisher's ‘t’ test was applied to test the significance of difference in Fat % and milk yield by pass fat feeding between the two groups. The ‘t’ value has been further compared with table value. If observed value found to be more than the table value, it is said to be significant (positively/negatively) at 0.05 level of significance, otherwise not. The statistical analysis of the data was done using software IBM-SPSS-20 (<http://www.spss.co.in>) and Micro Soft Excel-2010 (<http://office.microsoft.com>).

Results And Discussion

The findings of the present study as well as relevant discussion have been presented below. It was revealed from the Table 3 that due to supplementation of bypass fat feeding and mineral mixture, the milk yield per cow per day was increased by 5.5- 15.0 % in CB cows in treatment group and along with the improvement in post partum recovery of the body weight and body condition score and reproductive performance of the dairy animals has enhanced. Similar findings were also reported by (Naik, P.K. 2013). Milk composition and yield can be influenced by other factors including advancing age, genotype, body weight at kidding, gestation and dry periods, body condition, mastitis and frequency of milking, change in climate and feed, increased plane of nutrition, increasing the energy intake increases the milk production. (Y. Park 2010)

Standard Deviation	1.418	2.04			
Sample Variance	2.01	4.16			

* indicates significant of value at $p=0.05$

The data of daily dry matter intake and milk production were analyzed by T test as described by *Steel and Torrie (1992)*. The data presented in Table -3 revealed that the milk yield has increased by supplementation of bypass fat and mineral in the diet of dairy animals, also the milk yield has increased significantly by 15.0% over farmers general feed management practices. The findings were in line with the findings of (*Naik et al.2013*) and (*Wadhwa et al. 2012*). In the present findings improvement in the production performance was observed in the lactating cross-bred cows by feeding of bypass fat, similar findings have been reported by *Purshothaman (2004)* Similarly, *Kumar and Thakur (2007)*, and *Garg et al. (2008)* also reported significant improvement of milk yield in

ruminant due to sand *Sirohi and Walli,(2005)*. Since the calculated 't' value at $\alpha=0.05$ level was found to be larger than table value, indicating significant difference in milk yield between control and treatment group. It was concluded that the milk yield was significantly higher due to bypass fat and mineral feeding as compared to control group. When these studies were examined cautiously these indicated that all these studies were in early lactation period where the demand of nutrients remained the constraint for higher milk production and thus the supplementation of energy in the form of bypass fat had positive effect which leads to improvement in milk production of cows.

Table 4 – Effect of supplementation of bypass fat feeding on milk composition

Attributes	Change FAT% and SNF% in Milk					
	Control group	Treatment group	% increase	"t" calculated value	"t" table value	p- value
FAT %	3.97	4.61	16.12 %	3.191*	2.016	0.0026
SNF%	8.43	8.78	4.16 %	4.536*	2.002	0.00003
Total solids (%)	13.34	14.16	6.14 %	2.9002*	2.003	0.005316

* indicates significant of value at $p=0.05$

It is revealed from the above table -4 that supplementation by pass fat feeding and mineral mixture to the milching CB cows, had shown significant positive relationship with Fat % and SNF % in milk by supplementation of bypass fat feeding with mineral mixture along with concentrates to milching CB cows the fat percentage has increased 16.12 percentage and the SNF % has increased up to 4.16%. Milk fat per cent showed a clear cut rise with the bypass fat supplementation, similar findings were also reported by (*Mishra et al. 2004*), and (*Garg et al. 2008*). So it was concluded

from the experiment that by pass fat feeding with minerals and vitamins was more effective for C B cows as it has significantly increased the milk yield, FAT %, SNF % and Total solids % in milching cows. Milk composition varies between breeds; fat has the highest variation. It was concluded that significant increase in milk yield, fat percentage and TS percentage in milk as a result of feeding the bypass fat supplement. The findings were confirmed with the observation reported by (*Sirohi et al. 2010*)

Fig 1 : Change in fat % due to bypass fat feeding

It is concluded from the above table that the Fat % and SNF % of milk has increased after bypass fat feeding along with minerals and total solids % has been increased. Similar findings have been reported by (*Naik et al., 2009*). Present study concluded that bypass fat with minerals and vitamins was more effective to enhance Fat and SNF and Total solid in milching CB cows.

Body condition scoring evaluates fatness or thinness according to a five-point scale and scores are used to fine-tune dairy nutrition and health. Body condition influences productivity, reproduction, health, and longevity of dairy cattle. Thinness or fatness can be a clue to underlying nutritional deficiencies, health problems, or improper herd management. Body scoring is very

important in assessing the health status of an animal. A low score may indicate diseases or improper feeding while a high score may indicate high probability of breeding and metabolic problems. Body scoring is very important in assessing the health status of an animal. A low score may indicate diseases or improper feeding while a high score may indicate a high probability of breeding and metabolic problems. No fat in brisket or tail docks. A cow's body condition relates to her overall performance and that body condition scoring can be an important tool in dairy herd management, it is measured in five point scale from 1 to 5. Body condition scores (BCS) are an indirect estimate of energy balance. A score of 1 denotes a very thin cow, while 5 denotes an excessively fat cow, and 3 is an average body condition. Body score 1 has assigned where the animal is extremely thin, no fat in brisket or tail docks and skeletal structure are visible, may be diseased and survival is doubtful, and Body score 5 has assigned when the

animal is obese, flat appearance, brisket is heavy and bone structures not noticeable, back is fat and completely covered by fat, mobility impaired by large fat deposits, Condition scores range from 1, a very thin cow with no fat reserves, to 5, a severely over conditioned cow. Ideal condition scores fall in the range of 3.0-4.0 at dry off and calving and 2.5-3.5, at peak lactation, with no cows changing by more than 1 condition score class over any lactation period. In scoring a cow, the tail head and loin are the major areas to evaluate. Target scores help determine what condition to aim for during the different stages of lactation. If done on a regular basis, body condition scoring can improve dairy herd nutrition, health, and production. Proper conditioning, then, can be accomplished by body condition scoring, paying close attention to the animals, and ensuring that their nutrient requirements are being met, but not exceeded.

Table –5 Body score of animals during lactation period in control and treatment group

Parameter	Control group	Treatment group
Body condition score	2.4	3.1

(Body score in five point scale 1 to 5)

Regular monitoring of BCS can be useful in tracking changes over the lactation and in troubleshooting nutrition and health problems in the herd. It was revealed from the above table that due to proper feed

management and by pass fat feeding the health status of the animals has improved and body score was 3.1 which indicated good body conditions of cows during lactation period.

Table 6. Relationship between FAT% and SNF% of milk and selling price of milk

Control group			Treatment group			T value		p value
FAT %	SNF %	Price (Rs /lit)	FAT %	SNF %	Price (Rs /lit)	“t” cal Value	“t” table Value	
3.9	8.5	29.16	4.6	8.8	31.9446	6.252*	2.014	0.00

* indicates significant at 5% level

The data in above Table 6 average price of milk per lit as per fat% and SNF% was RS 29.20/lit as compared to Rs 32.90/lit in case of treatment group. And the price was high due to higher percentage of FAT and SNF%, by which farmers are getting more market price of their milk, the incremental price gain realized by the farmers was Rs 3.70 per lit of milk. It was due to higher fat% and SNF % in the milk due to feed supplementation of bypass fat feeding and mineral mixture and maintain proper hygienic milk production by the dairy farmers. There was positive significant relationship with Fat% and milk price. It was revealed from the above Table-6, that Feeding of the bypass fat to dairy animals has shown to give additional profit per

cow per day. The findings were in conformity with the observations of (Naik et al., 2009), and (Gowda et al., 2013). The experiments conducted under field conditions have demonstrated an increase of 10-15% milk in crossbred cows with the supplementation of bypass fat feeding which translates into a profit of Rs 50-80/- per day per animal for the dairy farmer.

Constraints faced by the cattle owners

Every farm faces problem while doing business, the problems may be associated with production or to the marketing. The problems faced by the dairy farmers in the study area were enumerated in the table-7.

Table –7 Constraints perceived by the dairy farmers

Sl no	Perceived constraints	Score	Rank
1	Inadequate feed and fodder	1.9	III
2	Higher feed cost	2.18	II
3	Input and services at more price	2.33	I
4	Low adoption of technologies	0.8	VI
5	Lack of subsidy	1.12	V
6	Lack of veterinary facilities	1.4	IV
7	Lack of marketing facility	0.6	VII

It was revealed from the Table- 7 that cost of input like feed medicine and cost for service providers and labour cost, high feed cost and in adequate feed and fodder are the important constraints faced by the farmers. Various inputs like feed concentrate, green fodder, dry fodder, labour, and veterinary services are needed for higher adoption of dairy farming as a source of income and livelihood support for the farmers in the district. So under such situation it is worth to examine whether dairy farming in this area is profitable or not. Marketing is a major component after production process, so sample farmers were asked to give their opinions about marketing related constraints. However the majority of the dairy farmers suggested that there was least problems in marketing of milk

as co-operative society OMFED ie, The Orissa State Cooperative Milk Producers Federation also known as OMFED is one of the Milk Federation affiliated to the National Dairy Development Board (NDDB) and other private milk processing corporate like Pragati Milk, and Milk-Moo are operating in the study area and milk marketing and procurement of milk is ensured due to established marketing channel and value chain in the District. Though cost of milk production was high, return from it was also high with positive net return from this enterprise. It was concluded that for good dairy business the best use of inputs like feed management, concentrate with dry fodder, green fodder and labour along with adequate veterinary service facilities must be ensured for larger adoption

profitable dairy farming in the district with some scope for value addition on milk product must be created for ensuring doubling the farmer's income.

Conclusion

From available literature, it can be concluded that supplementation of bypass fat in the diet of dairy animals is very important to alleviate problems of negative energy balance. Our results showed that bypass or inert fat supplementation to medium and/or high producing (10–20 kg/day) lactating crossbred cows is beneficial in terms of increasing milk production and fat corrected milk yield particularly in early lactation. Supplementation of bypass fat gives additional benefit due to increase in milk yield, more fat percentage in milk of the dairy animals. Feeding of the bypass fat to dairy animals has shown to give additional profit of Rs80/-per cow per day (Naik et al., 2009) and (Gowda et al., 2013). It was concluded that for good dairy business the best use of inputs like dry fodder, green fodder, concentrate and labour along with veterinary service facilities would be ensured. Though cost of milk production was high, return from it was also high with positive net return from this enterprise. It was concluded that for good dairy business the best use of inputs like dry fodder, green fodder, concentrate and labour along with veterinary service facilities were suggested.

References

1. Bindari, Y. R., Shrestha, S., Shrestha, N., & Gaire T.N. (2013). Effects of nutrition on reproduction- A review. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 4(1), 421-429.
2. Brishketu, K. and Thakur S. S. (2007). Effect of supplementing bypass fat on the performance of buffalo calves. *Indian Journal of Animal Nutrition* 24 (4): 233–36.
3. Chndel, S.R.S. (1998) A hand Book of Agricultural statistics, Achalnprakashan Mandir, Kanpur,
4. Edmonson, A. J., Lean I J., Weaver. D., Farver T, and Webster, G. (1989). A Body Condition Scoring Chart for Holstein Dairy Cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*. 72,(.1), 68-78.
5. Garg, M. R., Sherasia, P. L., Bhanderi, B. M., Gulati, S. K., Scott, T. W. (2008). Effect of feeding bypass fat supplement on milk production and characteristic of buffaloes. *Indian Journal of Dairy Science* 61 (1): 56–61.
6. Garg, M.R. and Meheta, A.K. (1998). Effect of feeding bypass fat on feed intake meat production and body condition of Holstein Friesian cows, *Indian jr of animal nutrition*. 15(4):242-245.
7. Heinrichs J., Coleen M. J., and Ishler A. (2020). Body Condition Scoring as a Tool for Dairy Herd Management, The Pennsylvania State, Penn State College of Agricultural Sciences research and extension programs Commonwealth of Pennsylvania, and the U.S. Department of Agriculture. page 1-5.
8. Mishra, S, Thakur S. S. and Tyagi, N. (2004). Milk production and composition in crossbred cows fed calcium salts of mustard oil fatty acids. *Indian Journal of Animal Nutrition* 21 (1): 22–25.
9. Naik, P.K. (2013). Bypass fat in dairy ration-A review. *Animal Nutrition and Feed Technology*, 13: 147-163.

10. Park, Y. (2010). Improving the safety and quality milk, wood head publishing series in Food Science, Technology and Nutrition, pages 304-346.
11. Prusty, S. R., Tripathy, S., Mishra, S. N. (2015). Problems and production Economics of Dairy Farmers in Cuttack District of Odisha, *Journal of Extn. Education*, Vol-XX, No -2, pp 179-185.
12. Purshothaman, S., Anil Kumar and Tiwari, D.P. (2008). Effect of Feeding Calcium Salts of Palm Oil Fatty Acids on Performance of Lactating Crossbred Cows. *Asian-Aust. J. Anim. Sci.*, 21 (3): 376-385.
13. Deka, R., Nath, K. C., Bhuyan, M., Nath N. C., Das, G. C., Deka, N. and Das, N. (2019). Effect of Nutritional Supplementation on Treatment of Anoestrus Swamp Buffalo Cows and Heifers, *International Journal of Live stock Rresearch* Vol 9(2), 55-63.
14. Ramteke, P.V., Patel, D.C., Parnerkar, S., Shankhpal, S.S., Patel, G.R., & Pandey, A. (2014). Effect of bypass fat supplementation during prepartum and postpartum on reproductive performance in buffaloes. *Livestock Research International*, 2(3), 54-58.
15. Rodenburg, J. (2004) - Dairy Cattle Production Systems Program Lead/OMAFRA, Body Condition Scoring of Dairy Cattle, Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural affairs.
16. Sahoo, J.K., Das, S.K., Sethy, K., Mishra, S.K., Swain, R.K., Mishra, P.C., & Satapathy, D. (2016). Effect of supplementation of mineral mixture and bypass fat on performance of crossbred cattle. *Journal of Animal Research*, 6 (4), 611-618.
17. Schroder, U. J., and Staufenbiel, R. (2006). Invited review: methods to determine body fat reserves in the dairy cow with special regard to ultrasonographic measurement of backfat thickness. *J. Dairy Sci.* 89, 1–14. doi: 10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(06)72064-1.
18. Sirohi, S. K. and Walli, T. K. (2005). Project report of the Consultancy project on Bypass fat feeding to crossbred animals. NDRI, Karnal.
19. Staples, C.R., Burke, J.M. and Thatcher, W.W. (1998). Influence of supplemental fats on reproductive tissues and performance of lactating cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 81, 856–871.
20. Steel, R.G.D. and Torrie, J.H (1992). Principles and Procedures of Statistics a Biometrical Approach. McGraw Hill, New York.
21. Sunil K. S., Walli T. K. and Mohanta R. K. (2010) Supplementation effect of bypass fat on production performance of lactating crossbred cows *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences* 80 (8): 733–736,
22. Vishal, M., Baghel. R.P.S., Ganie. A. and Srivastava, S. (2012). Effect of Bypass fat on intake and production performance of lactating crossbred cows, *Indian J. Anim. Res.*, 46 (1) : 103 – 104.
23. Wadhwa, M., Grewal, R.S., Bakshi, M.P.S. and Brar, P.S. (2012) Effect of supplementing bypass fat on the performance of high yielding crossbred cows. *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 82: 200- 203.